

Defossilising Agricultural Structures - Solutions and Pathways for Fossil-Energy-Free Farming

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Abstract

The continuous increase of the energy-consuming intensive agricultural production - heavily dependent on fossil-fuels - has negative effects in global warming and the environmental crisis in general. At the same time, however, it incorporates a great potential for a more sustainable production by adopting energy efficiency measures, practices, and technologies, as well as expanding the so far limited utilization of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), at farm level. To effectively address this worldwide challenge in the areas of agriculture and fossil fuel use reduction, AREA ZERO (Alliance for Renewable Energy in Agriculture and Zero Fossil Energy), was created from a collaboration of six innovative EU-funded projects working together on solutions to overcome current challenges still faced by the agricultural and livestock farming sectors. More specifically, its objectives include the utilization of technologies, techniques and strategies toward lower emissions, cleaner energy, improved energy efficiency, and cost effectiveness in the agricultural sector, designed to deliver tangible environmental, economic, and as well as social benefits.

Keywords: renewable energy sources, fossil-free agriculture, intensive livestock farming, sustainable agriculture.

1. Introduction

It is well documented that, in both European and global level, there is a clear correlation between energy use in modern agriculture and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions caused by its heavy dependence on fossil fuels (Rokicki et al., 2021; Paris et al, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c). In the area of industrialized production of crops, animals and animal products, energy is an indispensable resource. Intensive, mechanized agriculture uses considerable amounts of energy both directly, with the use of machinery and the control of the indoor environment of livestock buildings and greenhouses, as well as indirectly, e.g., to produce agrochemicals, farm machinery and buildings. Many studies have confirmed the relationship between energy consumption from different energy carriers in agriculture and productivity (Karkacier et al., 2006), as well as economic growth (Saudi et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019).

Energy efficiency in agriculture is one of the primary policy goals in countries with a significant agricultural sector (Inumula et al., 2020; Pamučar et al. 2020). A potential reduction in fossil energy use would decrease greenhouse gas emissions, as well as additional burdens on the environment (e.g., loss of biodiversity, soil depletion and the pollution of natural ecosystems). A shift towards RES technologies could effectively decouple energy use

from GHG emissions.

2. Policies towards environmental and agricultural sustainability

Climate change and environmental degradation constitute an existential threat worldwide. In European level, the European Green Deal has been put into action to overcome these challenges, with the aim to facilitate the transition to a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy. For this to be possible, net emissions of greenhouse gases must be eliminated by 2050, economic growth and resources use must be decoupled, without excluding no person and no place during the process.

The shift towards sustainable agriculture and food systems has been identified as instrumental in this process, acting as a link between a healthy planet and citizen's quality of life, and an integral part to an inclusive growth strategy. The above have been concretized in Fam-to-Fork Strategy, which, among others, aims to ensure food security in the face of climate change and biodiversity loss, reduce the environmental and climate footprint of the EU food system, while strengthening its resilience.

3. The need for an "Alliance for Renewable Energy in Agriculture and Zero Fossil Energy"

To that end, [AREA ZERO](#) cluster was formed. AREA ZERO is a collaboration of six EU-funded projects working together on solutions to overcome current challenges that the agricultural and livestock farming sectors are still facing.

Figure 2. Logo of AREA ZERO cluster.

Its main goals are to (i) enhance the collaboration toward improvement of energy efficiency in the European agriculture, (ii) maximize the impact and improve the quality and the relevance of the generated outputs, and (iii) further contribute to the 2050 climate goals of the EU. A short introduction to the AREA ZERO members' activities follows below.

3.1.1. AgroBioHeat

[AgroBioHeat](#) aims at mass deployment of improved and market ready agrobiomass heating solutions in rural areas of Europe. Its actions were mainly located in six European countries where an extensive national movement was created by the engagement, alignment of interests and creation of policy, financial and social conditions favouring the expansion of agrobiomass

heating.

3.1.2. HyPERFarm

[HyPERFarm](#) introduces the effective decarbonisation of farms by optimized agrivoltaic systems for energy self-sufficiency, while maintaining the crop yield in three pilots in Europe. Other key innovations that will be demonstrated in a cost-effective manner towards illustrating its business case and public acceptability include hydrogen production, intelligent climate control and e-driven pyrolysis.

3.1.3. RENAISSANCE

[RENAISSANCE](#) delivers in four European pilot sites a community-driven scalable and replicable approach, to implement new business models and technologies supporting clean production and shared distribution of energy in local communities. The project aims at developing a comprehensive benchmarking model to significantly improve the uptake of local integrated energy grids, reduce consumer prices future and identify their optimal configurations.

3.1.4. TheGreeFa

[TheGreeFa](#) aims to reduce the overall energy consumption in the greenhouses, maximise the available renewable energy for cooling, heating, and humidity control as well as water recovery water in hot and dry climate zones. Two different concepts are being developed and demonstrated in Continental and Mediterranean climates, introducing the concept of an innovative use of absorption processes utilizing thermo-chemical fluids.

3.1.5. AgroFossilFree

[AgroFossilFree](#) assesses the current energy status in EU agriculture and tries to identify the factors affecting innovation adoption and diffusion of Fossil-Energy-Free Technologies and Strategies (FEFTS). In such manner, it will pave the way to EU agriculture de-fossilisation by diminishing fossil energy dependence while maintaining end-product yield and quality and reducing environmental impact. The collaboration with stakeholders for creating policy guidelines to be immediately put into action in real agricultural activity is also at the project's core.

3.1.6. RES4LIVE

The overall objective of [RES4LIVE](#) is to provide advanced, cost-effective and market integrated technologies to the livestock sector that ensure the sustainability of the farms' operation, and the superior thermal comfort of the animals for increased productivity with minimum climate change impact. Case-sensitive, optimal designs combined with energy efficiency and other RES solutions are being demonstrated in four pilot farms across Europe, hosting swine, dairy and poultry, and evaluated technically, economically, environmentally, and socially, towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming.

4. Conclusions

It's time to reverse course and redesign our food producing practices in a way that suits the quality of life we need in the 21st century. Modern agriculture's heavy dependence on fossil fuels, renders sustainable food production and de-fossilisation of energy needs in agricultural facilities as crucial aspects worldwide. It is clearer than ever, especially under the current

circumstances of geopolitical turmoil and energy insecurity, that that intensification of research on possible solutions and pathways towards a fossil-energy-free farming is of utmost importance.

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